

METHODS OF WORKING WITH AUDIO TEXT IN TEACHING ENGLISH IN HIGH SCHOOL

Mirzanazarova Makhliyo Egamnazar kizi

Master's student

Kokand State Pedagogical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13932655>

Abstract. This article examines methods of working with audiotext in teaching English in high school. The methodology of teaching foreign languages is a system of knowledge about the laws of the process of teaching a foreign language and about the ways of influencing this process in order to optimize it.

Keywords: method, teaching, English, students, efficiency.

For effective teaching of listening, the choice of audio text is important. There are a number of requirements for texts for listening: educational value, interesting plot, informativeness, significance and reliability of the presented facts, compliance with the age level of the student's development and specific learning goals at different stages, authenticity of the text. Authentic texts are understood as texts "that native speakers produce for native speakers, that is, original texts created for real conditions, and not for a learning situation" [1-3]. Authentic, semi-authentic and educational texts are used to teach listening at school. For primary school, the most relevant texts may be children's songs, poems, fairy tales, stories, personal letters to a TV studio, cartoons, and for secondary school students (grades 5-9) - along with the above, announcers' announcements at the airport, at the train station, weather forecasts, as well as teen TV shows, videos. Both domestic and foreign methodologists traditionally suggest dividing the work on the text into three stages:

before listening

during listening

after listening

Pre-text stage. Preliminary instruction creates a motivational and organizational setting, mobilizes for active work. It includes the formulation of the task, explains the ways of its implementation, guides in difficulties, sometimes indicates forms of checking understanding. The degree of motivation of the listeners, and, consequently, the percentage of assimilation of the content, depends on the primary setting. In addition to strengthening motivation and formulating the setting for primary listening, the teacher must remove possible difficulties. The motivational setting shows the students what to pay attention

to, what difficulties will arise and how to organize their work in connection with them.

The teacher's task is to use a motivational setting to arouse the students' interest in the upcoming form of work. The most typical settings-tasks for this stage of working with the text:

1. Discussion of questions/statements before listening.
2. Guessing by the title/new words/illustrations.
3. A brief summary of the main topic by the teacher, introduction to the problems of the text.

The stage of actually listening to the text. When developing listening skills, there may be several listening, and it is important not to lose motivation. The novelty of the tasks will help with this:

- | | | |
|---|--|---|
| listen to the text and insert the missing words in the sentences; | listen to the text and say which of the suggested phrases were used in it without any changes; | listen to the text and say which definitions for the following words were found in it; |
| complete the following sentences; | listen to the text and say what was said in it about something; | listen to the text and find the Uzbek/English equivalent of the words in the parallel column. |

Post-text stage. After listening to the text and completing a series of exercises, you can continue to use it to develop your oral and written skills. Understanding can be checked in both a foreign language and your native language; in the traditional way or using tests. The criteria for assessing understanding of the content of the message you listened to depend primarily on how well the listener has managed to implement the communicative intention, the attitude. The listener's attitude can be related to understanding the basic and personally significant information, obtaining information that is valuable for

practical activities or for communication in a group [2]. In this regard, tasks for checking understanding of the text can be of three types:

The program of actions with the audio text should also include control. Before listening, students should be informed about how the result of understanding will be checked: should they answer questions after perceiving the text, complete a multiple choice test or a cloze test, make a plan for the text or put the proposed plan in order, write out key words or enter them in the proposed table, classifying them in accordance with the perceived information [1]. The palette of tasks for monitoring understanding is very diverse. The main criterion for choosing one or another control task is the purpose of working with the audio text and the type of listening: global, selective, detailed.

Examples of tasks to check understanding after listening:

- Confirm or refute statements;
- Select illustrations for the text;
- Arrange the plan points;
- Mark the route plan on the map;
- Complete a multiple-choice test (out of 3-4 statements, one is correct, the rest are distractors);
- Complete a restoration test (students listen to the text twice. The second time, the text is presented with gaps at pre-determined intervals, for example, every 7th word. The students' task is to write down the missing words in order.);
- Complete an alternative test (yes - no, "+", "-");
- Select the title of the text from several proposed options;
- Determine the number of semantic parts;
- Draw what you heard in the form of a picture.

Sometimes, after completing a test task, you can ask students to exchange notebooks, check each other's words using the key and evaluate the correctness of the tasks. If listening control is not regular, then one cannot count on its effectiveness. It is important that control covers all students. It is necessary to take into account the different complexity of control techniques, start with simpler techniques that require a minimum of productive forms of speech in a foreign language, for example, answers to general questions, and gradually move on to more complex ones ("characterize", "explain why"). When using techniques related to speech activity, it is necessary to take into account the language training of schoolchildren. Forms of control should be related to understanding of varying degrees of depth: from explanation of superficial facts to deep ones.

References:

1. Abdug'afurovich, R. B. (2022). Innovation Technologies in Teaching English. American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research, 3(6), 288-291.
2. Botirova, P. H., Inomiddinova, D. I., & Sobirova, R. M. (2019). Methodological recommendations for using the method of work in small groups. In Umumta'lim maktablari dasturi, Chet tillar, O'qituvchi, T., 1996.
3. Humoyunbek E. A. (2021). Methods used in teaching students english. Scientific progress, 1 (6), 944-950.

